

International Workshop "Education, Psychology, and Sociology in the Current Century"

Hybrid – online & in-person
 March 15, 2024, Paris, FRANCE

Registration of the participants	08.00-08.30
Event welcome	08.30-08.45
Plenary speakers	08.45-11.00
<i>MIHAI COVACI, Hyperion University & CBM International University</i> Education and Psychology in the Current Social View. Evidence from Mountain Area	08.45-09.15
<i>BRINDUSA STERPU, Centre for Mountain Economy & CBM International University</i> Education and Social Sciences in the Current Mountain Perspective	09.15-10.45
Q & A	10.45-11.00
Parallel sessions	11.00-12.00
<i>Session 1 – Social Sciences in Art and Humanity</i> <i>EVA CLARK, Akademos Learning UK</i> Exploring the Intersection of Social Sciences, Art, and Humanity	11.00-11.30
<i>ALBERT LEWIS, 9462-9755 Quebec Canada</i> The Fusion of Social Sciences and the Arts: Perspectives on Humanity	11.30-12.00
<i>Session 2 – Education, Psychology, and Social Sciences, with local and regional focus</i> <i>JACK BAILEY, Centre for Risk Studies in Economic and Social Sciences Austria</i> Localized Approaches in Education, Psychology, and Social Sciences:	11.00-11.30

CBM International University USA
 Akademos Learning UK
 9462-9755 Quebec CA & AT (Centre for Risk Studies in Economic and Social Sciences)

<p>Regional Insights and Impacts</p> <p><i>OLIVIA CAMPBELL, Zealandina Agency UK</i></p> <p>Regional Dimensions in Education, Psychology, and Social Sciences: A Localized Perspective</p>	11.30-12.00
<p>Coffee break</p>	12.00-12.15
<p><i>Session 1 – Education, Psychology, and Sciences in Art and Humanity</i></p> <p><i>CARLA SELMA, Akademos Agency UK</i></p> <p>Integrating Education, Psychology, and Sciences within Arts and Humanities</p> <p><i>PARVATI AARAV, CBM International University</i></p> <p>Bridging Education, Psychology, and Science with the Arts and Humanities</p>	12.15-12.45 12.45-13.15
<p><i>Session 2 - Education, Psychology, and Social Sciences, with local and regional focus</i></p> <p><i>LASHMI DURGA, CBM International University</i></p> <p>Examining Education, Psychology, and Social Sciences through Local and Regional Lenses</p> <p><i>SHI CHEN, CBM International University</i></p> <p>Education, Psychology, and Social Sciences: Local and Regional Perspectives for Deeper Insight</p>	12.15-12.45 12.45-13.15
<p>Q&A</p>	13.15-13.45
<p>Concluding remarks</p>	13.45-14.00

Location: 73 Rue de Vaugirard, Paris, 75006, France